

TPHO: a time-dependent photoionisation model for AGN outflows*

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ABSTRACT

Outflows in active galactic nuclei (AGN) are considered a promising candidate for driving AGN feedback at large scales. However, without information on the density of these outflows, we cannot determine how much kinetic power they are imparting to the surrounding medium. Monitoring the response of the ionisation state of the absorbing outflows to changes in the ionising continuum provides the recombination timescale of the outflow, which is a function of the electron density. We have developed a new self-consistent time-dependent photoionisation model, `tpho`, enabling the measurement of the plasma density through time-resolved X-ray spectroscopy. The algorithm solves the full time-dependent energy and ionisation balance equations in a self consistent fashion for all the ionic species. The model can therefore reproduce the time-dependent absorption spectrum of ionized outflows responding to changes in the ionizing radiation of the AGN. We find that when the ionised gas is in a non-equilibrium state its transmitted spectra are not accurately reproduced by standard photoionisation models. Our simulations with the current X-ray grating observations show that the spectral features identified as a multiple-components warm absorbers, might be in fact features of a time-changing warm absorber and not distinctive components. The `tpho` model facilitates accurate photoionisation modelling in the presence of a variable ionising source, thus providing constraints on the density and in turn the location of the AGN outflows. Ascertaining these two parameters will provide important insight into the role and impact of ionised outflows in AGN feedback.

Keywords: TBD

1. INTRODUCTION

Accreting super-massive black holes (with mass between $10^6 - 10^9 M_{\odot}$) are the central engines of active galactic nuclei (AGN). About half of Seyfert I galaxies show outflows of material in form of ultra-fast outflows, warm absorbers, and ionised/neutral/molecular outflows (e.g., Costantini et al. 2007; Fabian 2012; Tombesi et al. 2013; Veilleux et al. 2013; Kaastra et al. 2014; Tombesi et al. 2015; Fiore et al. 2017; Laha et al. 2021). In the last decades, the potential importance of AGN outflows for the growth of super-massive black holes, the enrichment of the intergalactic medium, the evolution of the host galaxy, cluster cooling flows and the luminosity function of AGN has been widely recognised (Fabian 2012; Gaspari et al. 2020).

X-ray spectroscopy is a powerful tool to study ionised outflows closer to the central region. Measurement of absorp-

tion line spectra yield reliable information on different aspects of the outflows such as their kinematics (turbulence and outflow velocity) and ionisation state. Spectral studies of warm absorbers highlight their complex multiphase structure, which spans a wide range of ionisation parameters, $\log(\xi/\text{erg cm s}^{-1}) = -1$ to 3, and column densities, $N_{\text{H}} = 10^{21-23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (Blustin et al. 2005; McKernan et al. 2007; Krongold et al. 2009; Tombesi et al. 2013; Laha et al. 2014; Behar et al. 2017). They are usually detected as absorption lines and edges from H-like and He-like ions of the most abundant elements, such as C, O, N, Ne, Mg, Si, Si and Fe, in the soft spectra below 2 keV (Crenshaw et al. 2003; Mehdipour et al. 2010, 2018; Ebrero et al. 2021). Low ionisation absorbers ($\log \xi = 0 - 1.5$) imprint deep spectral absorption troughs in the rest frame wavelength 15–17 Å due to the blended Fe M shell unresolved transitions array (UTA; Behar et al. 2001). All these spectral features are always found blueshifted with respect to the systematic redshift, implying

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59 that these absorbers are outflowing with a velocity, v_{out} , be-
60 tween ~ 100 and ~ 5000 km s $^{-1}$ (Laha et al. 2021).

61 Spectroscopy on its own does not provide information re-
62 garding the distance r of the absorber material to the central
63 ionising source. This can be seen within the definition of the
64 ionisation parameter $\xi = L_{\text{ion}}/(n_e r^2)$ where L_{ion} is the ionis-
65 ing luminosity of the source facing the cloud (integrated be-
66 tween 1 – 1000 Ryd) and n_e is the electron density of the gas
67 (Tarter et al. 1969; Krolik et al. 1981). With L_{ion} and ξ known
68 from observations, only the product $n_e r^2$ can be determined.
69 This degeneracy makes it challenging to assess the signifi-
70 cance of ionised outflows in AGN feedback. The energetics
71 of a spherical shell-like outflow can be quantified by the mass
72 outflow rate, $\dot{M}_{\text{out}} \simeq 1.23 m_p N_H r v_{\text{out}} \Omega$ and kinetic luminosity,
73 $\dot{E}_k = \frac{1}{2} \dot{M}_{\text{out}} v_{\text{out}}^2$, where the constant 1.23 takes into account
74 the abundances of elements, m_p is the proton mass, and Ω is
75 the solid angle subtended by the outflow, which is expected
76 to be $\sim \pi$ (Blustin et al. 2005). Determining these two quan-
77 tities requires precise measurements of the outflow distance
78 to the central source.

79 A common approach to characterising the outflow loca-
80 tion is measuring the density n_e of the plasma and deriving
81 the distance through the definition of the ionisation param-
82 eter. One way to constrain the density via spectroscopy is
83 to use density-sensitive absorption lines from metastable lev-
84 els (Kraemer et al. 2006; Arav et al. 2015). This method
85 is widely used in UV spectroscopy, where these metastable
86 transitions of C II*, C III*, S III* and Fe II* are commonly de-
87 tected. In the X-ray band, the density diagnostic of AGN
88 outflows using absorption lines is not very effective. Low
89 signal to noise ratio of these rather weak X-ray lines makes
90 their density diagnostic inaccessible in most AGN (Kaastra
91 et al. 2004; King et al. 2012; Mao et al. 2017). Only the en-
92 hanced sensitivity of future X-ray telescopes, such as *Arcus*
93 (Smith et al. 2016) and *Athena* (Nandra et al. 2013), and their
94 broader wavelength range will enable the detection of the
95 density sensitive lines in the X-ray band opening the doors
96 for a new kind of diagnostic in AGN outflows (Kaastra 2017).

97 An alternative method to estimate the gas density is a spec-
98 tral analysis of density sensitive emission lines. The ratio
99 between the recombination, intercombination and forbidden
100 emission lines in the He-like triplets varies as a function of
101 the plasma density (Porquet et al. 2010). In the literature
102 there are several studies of the He-like triplets in emission
103 from photoionised plasma in AGN where the upper limits
104 of the density are derived (Porquet & Dubau 2000; Collinge
105 et al. 2001; McKernan et al. 2003). However, these spectral
106 analyses are not only limited by the instrumental sensitivity,
107 but also by Li-like absorption lines which can significantly
108 diminish the intensity of the intercombination line in a pho-
109 toionised medium, leading to more uncertain density diag-
110 nostic (Mehdipour et al. 2015).

111 The approach that we adopt in this work to determine the
112 gas density is a timing analysis of the response timescale of
113 the plasma to changes in the ionising radiation. How fast the
114 gas responds depends on the recombination timescale, which
115 is a function of the gas density (see Section 2 for a detailed
116 description). Early time-dependent photoionisation studies
117 used only a few spectral features (the most significant) to
118 measure the delay (or the lack of delay) of the ionisation state
119 of the gas relative to the ionising luminosity variation. This
120 constrains the recombination timescale and consequently the
121 density and the distance.

122 First attempts of tracing the gas variability with low-
123 resolution CCD instruments, such as *BeppoSAX* and *ASCA*
124 were done studying the evolution of the X-ray absorption
125 edges (Morales et al. 2000). However, the higher energy res-
126 olution of the grating on board *XMM-Newton* (den Herder
127 et al. 2001) and *Chandra* (Canizares et al. 2005) allowed to
128 meaningfully follow the variation of strong absorption lines.
129 For example, Behar et al. (2003) tracked the response of the
130 multi-phase warm absorber in RGS data of NGC 3783 inves-
131 tigating the evolution of O VII and O VIII lines for the high-
132 ionisation component and the Fe UTA for the low-ionisation
133 component. For the same source, Reeves et al. (2004) analy-
134 ses the variability of the Fe xxv line due to the presence of a
135 possible higher ionisation component.

136 Subsequently, broad-band time-dependent photoionisation
137 models have been applied to large *XMM-Newton* and *Chan-*
138 *dra* campaign such as Mrk 509 (Kaastra et al. 2012),
139 NGC 5548 (Ebrero et al. 2016), and NGC 7469 (Behar et al.
140 2017; Mehdipour et al. 2018; Peretz et al. 2018). The com-
141 plex multi-component outflow in NGC 4051 is one of the best
142 studied cases among Seyfert I galaxies (Silva et al. 2016).
143 NGC 4051 is a particularly bright and variable Seyfert I
144 galaxy. Nicastro et al. (1999) and Krongold et al. (2007)
145 suggested a quick response of the absorber ionisation to the
146 continuum level that places the absorber as close as 0.003
147 pc. Recently, Wang et al. (2022) studied the response of
148 an ionized obscurer in NGC 3227, suggesting a location of
149 $0.001 \text{ pc} \lesssim r \lesssim 0.1 \text{ pc}$ from the central source, whereas the
150 warm absorbers are further out ($0.01 \text{ pc} \lesssim r \lesssim 100 \text{ pc}$).

151 Here we present a new Time-dependent PHotoionisation
152 model, *tpho*, based on the methodology followed by Kaa-
153 *stra* et al. (2012) and Silva et al. (2016). We have upgraded
154 the photoionisation code *pion* (Mehdipour et al. 2016) to
155 treat non-photoionisation equilibrium state conditions. The
156 ultimate goal of the model is to derive the density and
157 therefore the location of the AGN outflows through precise
158 high-resolution X-ray spectral-timing analysis. In Section 2,
159 we describe the time-dependent effects that have been in-
160 tegrated in the new photoionisation model. In Section 3,
161 we show three different applications of the model to de-
162 scribe the impact of time-dependent effects on the inferred

163 plasma physical properties such as temperature, ionic con-
 164 centration, heating and cooling rates, etc. The importance
 165 of the time-dependent effects in high-resolution X-ray spec-
 166 troscopy studies of AGN outflows is discussed in Section 4.

167 2. TIME-EVOLVING IONISATION STATE

168 Traditionally, modelling of astronomical photoionised
 169 plasma is done assuming the condition of steady-state equi-
 170 librium, which means that the gas ionisation is balanced by
 171 recombination, atomic excitations are balanced by sponta-
 172 neous and induced de-excitations, and electron heating is bal-
 173 anced by cooling. In this equilibrium condition, it is possible
 174 to calculate the distribution of the ionic species in a cloud of
 175 optically thin gas illuminated by an intense ionising luminos-
 176 ity by setting the photoionisation rate equal to the radiative
 177 recombination rate (see [Netzer 1990](#)) and adding the condi-
 178 tion for charge conservation ([Blandford et al. 1990](#)).

179 The steady equilibrium assumption is valid only if L_{ion} is
 180 not varying in time or if the equilibrium timescales for re-
 181 combination, photoionisation and thermal balance are much
 182 shorter than variability timescales in the ionising continuum.
 183 Whenever the illuminating radiation changes on timescales
 184 shorter than the equilibrium timescales, it is necessary to take
 185 into account the full time-dependent form of the ionisation
 186 balance equations. By definition, the relative density $n_{X,i}$ of
 187 ion i of a certain element X varies with time as a function
 188 of the electron density, n_e , the recombination rate from stage
 189 $i + 1$ to i (given by the recombination coefficient $\alpha_{X,i+1 \rightarrow i}$)
 190 times the electron density) and the ionisation rate from stage i
 191 to $i+1$. Gathering the contribution by photoionisation, Comp-
 192 ton ionisation, collisional ionisation and Auger ionisation in
 193 the ionisation coefficient $\gamma_{X,i \rightarrow i+1}$, the time-dependent ioni-
 194 sation balance equation is written as follows ([Krolik & Kriss](#)
 195 [1995](#)):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dn_{X,i}}{dt} &= (n_{X,i+1}n_e\alpha_{X,i+1 \rightarrow i}) - (n_{X,i}n_e\alpha_{X,i \rightarrow i-1}) + \\ &+ \sum_{k=1}^{i-1} (n_{X,i-1-k}\gamma_{X,i-1 \rightarrow i}) - \sum_{k=1}^i (n_{X,i-k}\gamma_{X,i \rightarrow i+1}). \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

196 The equation represents the sum of the destruction (second
 197 and fourth terms) and formation rate (first and third terms)
 198 of each ion considering several processes of ionisation and
 199 radiative recombination. The two ionisation terms take into
 200 account all forms of ionization in SPEX, including the inner-
 201 shell ionization that can induce additional multiple ionisa-
 202 tions. In case of photoionisation equilibrium, photoionisa-
 203 tion dominates over the other ionisation processes including
 204 collisional ionisation.

205 The solution of Equation 1 defines the photoionisation
 206 timescales, t_{ph} , and recombination, t_{rec} , timescales which to-
 207 gether measure the time necessary for a plasma with den-

208 sity n_e to reach photoionisation equilibrium with the ionis-
 209 ing continuum for an increasing or decreasing flux phase,
 210 respectively. For each point of the light curve of L_{ion} , these
 211 timescales can be approximated by the inverse of the destruc-
 212 tion rate of the ion i of the element X which define the equi-
 213 librium timescale, t_{eq} ([Krolik & Kriss 1995](#); [Nicastrò et al.](#)
 214 [1999](#)):

$$t_{\text{eq}}^{X^i: X^{i+1}} \sim \frac{1}{\alpha_{X,i+1 \rightarrow i} n_e} \cdot \left[\frac{1}{-(\alpha_{X,i \rightarrow i-1} / \alpha_{X,i+1 \rightarrow i}) + (n_{X,i+1} / n_{X,i})} \right]. \quad (2)$$

215 Thus the plasma will reach equilibrium with the ionising
 216 source after a time delay t_{eq} . Equation 1 shows that the time
 217 necessary for a gas to reach equilibrium critically depends
 218 on the characteristic electron density n_e of the plasma. High-
 219 density clouds reach the photoionisation equilibrium in short
 220 timescales by quickly responding to changes in the ionis-
 221 ing continuum. On the other hand, low-density gases need
 222 more time to achieve the ionisation balance with the ionis-
 223 ing radiation. Especially in this late response scenario due
 224 to low-density absorbers it is important to consider the time-
 225 dependent effect in the photoionisation modelling.

226 The behaviour of the time-variation of ionic abundances
 227 depends on two factors: first the ratio $t_{\text{eq}}/t_{\text{var}}$, where t_{var} is
 228 the typical timescale on which most of the fluctuations in the
 229 ionising radiation occurs. Second it depends on the coeffi-
 230 cient of variation (i.e. the ratio of the standard deviation to
 231 the mean) of the ionising continuum which quantify the am-
 232 plitude of the flux fluctuations. We describe here the time-
 233 dependent effects identifying three different scenarios:

- 234 • *equilibrium state*: when $t_{\text{eq}} \ll t_{\text{var}}$ the plasma ionisa-
 235 tion state is constantly in equilibrium with the ionising
 236 radiation. Under this condition, a large variation of the
 237 ionising continuum would lead to a significant change
 238 of the ionisation state. Either a very high density ab-
 239 sorber or a slowly variable ionising source could lead
 240 to the equilibrium condition.
- 241 • *non-equilibrium steady state*: when $t_{\text{eq}} \gg t_{\text{var}}$ the ionic
 242 concentrations do not respond to the ionization flux
 243 reaching a steady state defined by the ionisation and re-
 244 combination states. The plasma is therefore constantly
 245 out of equilibrium with the ionising continuum. How-
 246 ever, if the amplitude of the source variability is small,
 247 the differences from the mean are modest. This steady-
 248 state condition is common in scenarios with either very
 249 low-density absorbers, or a rapidly variable ionising
 250 source, or both.
- 251 • *delayed state*: when $t_{\text{eq}} \sim t_{\text{var}}$ the plasma ionic con-
 252 centrations evolve smoothly and with a delay relative
 253 to the ionising luminosity variability. The plasma is
 254 neither in equilibrium nor in a non-equilibrium steady
 255 state.

state. This is in principle the most interesting case since the time delays between the ionisation state of the plasma and the ionising luminosity is effectively used to constrain the density of the ionising source.

Consequently, a time-dependent photoionisation analysis of a plasma in equilibrium-state or in non-equilibrium steady state will only allow us to derive, respectively, a lower and an upper bound on the gas density, which correspond to an upper and lower limit on its distance, respectively. Instead, observing the time delay on which the absorbing outflow responds to the ionising continuum will allow to constrain its location more precisely.

In order to understand which case applies to a plasma it is crucial to estimate both t_{eq} and t_{var} . In general, the power spectral density of fluctuations or the excess variance of the light curve (e.g., Nandra et al. 1997; Ponti et al. 2012) help to determine the variability of the ionising continuum. The estimate of t_{eq} is even more complicated since according to Equation 2 it requires the knowledge of the density and ionisation state (thus the ionic concentrations, $n_{X,i}$) of the absorbing plasma. In Figure 1, we show the recombination timescale, which is a good approximation of t_{eq} , as a function of the gas density assuming a typical type-1 AGN ionising continuum. In specific, we adopt the ionising spectral energy distribution (SED) of Mrk 509 taken from Mehdipour et al. (2011) to compute the recombination timescales. In the *top* panels we display the t_{rec} of all the relevant ions of oxygen and iron for a plasma with $\log \xi = 2.0$. The recombination timescale of different ions can vary by orders of magnitude from one ion to the next, even for ions of the same element. Different elements reach their equilibrium on different timescales.

In the *bottom* panels of Figure 1 we show how the recombination timescale of a single ion (O VIII and Fe XXVI) relates to the ionisation state of the plasma using a grid of $\log \xi$ spanning between -1 and 6. The ionisation level of the plasma leads the concentrations of the ionic species and consequently their recombination timescales. When the ionic concentrations reaches their maximum (in this case, $\log \xi \sim 2.0$ and $\log \xi \sim 4.0$ for O VIII and Fe XXVI, respectively) the ions require a longer time to reach the equilibrium. Moreover, the fact that we observe a larger scatter for O VIII with respect to Fe XXVI is due to their different ionic concentration distribution: O VIII has a broader distribution than Fe XXVI (see for example Figure 6 of Mehdipour et al. 2016).

Finally, when characterising a time-evolving ionised plasma it is important to include the cooling timescale, which indicates the time necessary for a gas to cool down. As we will show in the following section, the cooling timescale has a significant impact on the time evolution of the concentration of the plasma ions.

3. A NEW TIME-DEPENDENT PHOTOIONISATION MODEL

Commonly-used photoionisation models are limited by the assumption that the plasma is constantly in ionisation and excitation equilibrium. Therefore, they are only suitable to describe the absorbers found in the *equilibrium* case when $t_{\text{eq}} \ll t_{\text{var}}$. Using the standard photoionisation models to characterise the other two scenarios described in Section 2 would lead to a wrong conclusion since the ionisation state of the plasma is in non-photoionisation equilibrium. In order to correctly characterise such absorbers, we developed a time-dependent photoionisation model (tpho) which accounts for the time-dependency of the ionizing and recombining processes that take place in a photoionised plasma together with all the relevant heating and cooling processes. The ultimate goal of this model is to determine the location of the AGN outflows and consequently their energetic properties (kinetic power, momentum outflow rate, outflow mass rate), which are crucial to understand the AGN feedback mechanism.

In the following section, we describe the tpho model in detail explaining the algorithm and its inputs and outputs. Subsequently, to illustrate the time-dependent effects, we apply the model to two didactic cases characterised by a sudden increase and decrease of the ionising luminosity (Section 3.2 and 3.3, respectively). This simple cases allow us to study how the temperature, the heating/cooling rates and the ionic concentrations evolves when the gas is not any more assumed to be in photoionisation equilibrium. We also compare the time evolution of close ions (e.g. O VIII and O IX) and ions of different elements (i.e. oxygen and iron) for different densities.

A more realistic case will be examined in Section 3.4, where we calculate the time-dependent effects introduced by a flaring light curve. This specific example highlights the three scenarios explained in Section 2 and the density range in which the model is sensitive for a given time variability. Finally, we compute the time evolution of the X-ray transmission of the plasma and compare it with the equilibrium solution in Section 3.5 to understand the importance of the time-dependent effects in a time-resolved X-rays spectroscopy analysis.

3.1. TPHO model

The tpho model enables a realistic characterisation of the evolution of the ionisation state of plasma exposed to a variable photoionising source. The model has been implemented in the X-ray fitting code SPEX¹ (Kaastra et al. 1996) and released to the community with the 3.07 version of the software Kaastra et al. (2022).

¹ <https://spex-xray.github.io/spex-help/index.html>

Figure 1. Recombination timescale as a function of the density of a plasma in photoionisation equilibrium. In the top panels we show the recombination timescale of the oxygen (left) and iron (right) ions for a plasma with an ionisation parameter of $\log \xi = 2$. We show only the ions which have a relative concentration larger than 10^{-6} . In the bottom panels, we display the recombination timescales of the H-like ion of oxygen (left) and iron (right) for a grid of ionisation parameters.

356 The code evaluates the time evolution of all ionic concentrations for the elements with an atomic number between 1
 357 (H) and 30 (Zn). To do so, it solves the set of N coupled ordinary first-order differential equations shown in Equation 1,
 358 which is analytically solvable only for $N = 2$. We solve all these equations simultaneously using the subroutine `solcon`
 359 of `SPEX` which is based on the work of [Kaastra & Jansen \(1993\)](#). The method consists of the calculation on the fly
 360 of the transition matrix which contains all the ionisation and recombination rates for a grid of temperatures and ionisation
 361 parameters. Eigenvalues and eigenvectors of these matrix are also calculated. The ionisation balance is computed at small
 362 steps according to the time evolution of ionisation and temperature in the plasma. Finally, the eigenvector decomposition
 363 and the calculated coefficients are used to evaluate the ionic concentrations at each time step.
 364

372 The code calculates the evolution of several heating and cooling processes: photoionisation, Compton scattering and
 373 ionisation, Auger electrons, free-free absorption, collisional de-excitation, and external heating for the heating rates
 374 whereas radiative recombination, collisional ionisation, inverse Compton scattering, bremsstrahlung, collisional exci-
 375 tation, and dielectronic recombination for the cooling rates.
 376
 377

378 tion, and dielectronic recombination for the cooling rates.
 379 Cooling is assessed using the time-dependent ion abundances. The difference between the total cooling and heating
 380 processes is used to determine the temporal evolution of the plasma temperature.
 381

382 The `tpho` model needs several inputs for the determination of the time-evolution of the ionisation balance. For the initial
 383 conditions of the plasma, the model adopts photoionisation equilibrium in order to start the evolution of the plasma. The
 384 spectral shape of the ionising continuum is also necessary to determine the photoionisation rates. The `tpho` model can,
 385 like `pion`, take the spectral energy distribution directly from the continuum components set by the user in `SPEX`. Alternatively,
 386 the SED can be provided via an input file. The variability of the ionising luminosity is also required to determine
 387 the time-evolution of the ionic concentrations. The code uses the light curve of the ionising luminosity to interpolate the
 388 ionisation parameter. The last fundamental parameter necessary to solve the time-dependent ionisation balance equations
 389 is the density of the plasma, n_{H} , which is the parameter of interest, and can be either fixed or fitted to the data in the `tpho`
 390 model.
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400 The main outputs of the code are the ionic concentrations
 401 of all the elements, the heating/cooling rates and the plasma
 402 temperature as a function of time. We plot the outputs of
 403 the model in the following sections for three simple cases
 404 highlighting their dependence on the gas density. The `tpho`
 405 code then uses the obtained ionic concentrations to calculate
 406 the corresponding absorption and emission spectrum of the
 407 plasma at each time step. Thus, a time-resolved spectrum
 408 taken at time t , can be fitted by applying the corresponding
 409 `tpho` spectrum that is calculated at time t .

410 3.2. Light curve case: step-up function

411 In order to examine the evolution of ionic concentrations
 412 calculated with `tpho`, and compare them with the equilib-
 413 rium scenario (`pion`) we adopt the simplest case of a step-up
 414 function light curve. In this case, we assume that the ionising
 415 flux goes from a *low* to a *high* state almost instantaneously
 416 ($\Delta t \sim 0.01$ s) with a factor 10 change in flux. The light curve
 417 is shown in the upper panel of Figure 2. For the initial condi-
 418 tion we considered an optically thin gas cloud with an initial
 419 ionisation parameter of $\log \xi = 2$ and illuminated by the
 420 SED of Mrk 509 (Mehdipour et al. 2011). With the `tpho`
 421 model we computed the time evolution of the ionic concen-
 422 trations for a grid of hydrogen densities ranging between 10^4
 423 and 10^{10} cm^{-3} .

424 The time-dependent behaviour of the concentration of
 425 O VIII, O IX, Fe XIX, and Fe XX are shown in Figure 2. For
 426 different hydrogen densities the ionic concentrations follows
 427 the same exponential evolution but they systematically shift
 428 over different timescales. The shift is driven by the differ-
 429 ent density of the gas. Plotting the ionic concentration as a
 430 function of $n_{\text{H}} \cdot \text{time}$ the curves will perfectly overlap (see for
 431 example top panel of Figure 6).

432 Ions in dense gases (yellow shades) reach their equilib-
 433 rium concentration faster than the ions in less dense gases
 434 (blue shades). For comparison, we also calculated the ionic
 435 concentration curve for a gas in photoionisation equilibrium
 436 using the `pion` model (black stars). Interestingly, the evolu-
 437 tion of the ionic concentration curves calculated with `tpho`
 438 appears different from the equilibrium one. All the four ions
 439 show a flattening in their evolution which is closely related
 440 to the time-evolution of plasma temperature.

441 In the *top* panel of Figure 3, we illustrate how the tem-
 442 perature of the gas evolves considering the same step-up
 443 light curve described above. When considering the time-
 444 dependent effects the gas reaches the equilibrium tempera-
 445 ture after a significant time delay with respect to a gas
 446 in ionisation equilibrium (black stars). This time delay in-
 447 creases with decreasing gas density. High-density gas with
 448 $n_{\text{H}} = 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ takes ~ 10 ks to reach the equilibrium tem-
 449 perature whereas low-density gases ($n_{\text{H}} < 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) can take
 450 a few years ($t > 10^5$ ks) to reach the equilibrium value.

451 The plasma temperature is evaluated summing the total
 452 heating and cooling rates shown in the second panel of Fig-
 453 ure 3: the temperature increases when the heating is larger
 454 than the cooling and is constant when the two processes be-
 455 come equivalent. The total amount of energy injected into
 456 the plasma strongly depends on the density of the plasma.
 457 The heating curves (solid lines) increase during the jump
 458 from low to high flux level. As soon as the ionising radi-
 459 ation reaches the high state, the heating rate in high density
 460 gas starts to drop. The cooling rates (dashed lines) start out
 461 as constant, but kick in at late times. These late changes in
 462 the heating and cooling rates, alongside temperature, natu-
 463 rally alters the ionic concentrations, making them rise or de-
 464 cline depending on the ion. Indeed, at around the time of the
 465 second decline/rise in ionic concentration shown in Figure
 466 2, there are noticeable deviations in the total cooling/heating
 467 rates.

468 In the third panel of Figure 3, we compare the shapes of
 469 the heating-rate curves which were computed fixing the ini-
 470 tial ionisation parameter of the plasma. The curves show an
 471 extended peak close to their maximum heating rate value.
 472 The duration of this peak anti-correlates with the gas density.
 473 This shows again that denser plasmas react more quickly to
 474 incoming radiation. In the *bottom* panel, we show the con-
 475 tribution to the total of the different heating and cooling pro-
 476 cesses considered in the calculations for a gas with a density
 477 of $n_{\text{H}} = 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. For the considered ionising continuum,
 478 the heating is dominated by photoionisation. Auger electrons
 479 and Comptonisation contribute less ($\sim 10\%$ and $< 1\%$, re-
 480 spectively) and all the rest of the processes listed in the be-
 481 ginning of Section 3.1 can be neglected here. Collisional
 482 excitation, radiative recombination and bremsstrahlung are,
 483 instead, the major cooling processes.

484 3.3. Step-down light curve

485 To compare the previous study case with a scenario where
 486 the cooling rates and the recombination processes are ex-
 487 pected to dominate, we repeated the same investigation but
 488 for a step-down light curve function: the ionising continuum
 489 goes from high to low flux level by a factor of 10 (see light
 490 curve in the *top* panel of Figure 4). To reproduce exactly the
 491 opposite of the previous test we assumed the SED shape of
 492 Mrk 509 and an ionisation parameter of $\log \xi = 3$ as initial
 493 condition.

494 In Figure 4, we show the time evolution of the O VIII, O IX,
 495 Fe XIX, and Fe XX concentrations. As shown before, the time
 496 necessary for each ionic concentration to reach their equi-
 497 librium values depends on their density. However, the ionic
 498 concentration curves do not follow the reverse pattern of the
 499 step-up light curve case shown before (Section 3.2), as it
 500 would be expected for a plasma in ionisation equilibrium.

Figure 2. Step-up light curve case: the light curve is shown in the top panel. The ionising flux increases by a factor of ten in 0.01 s. In the panels below we show the time-dependent evolution of the concentration relative to hydrogen of O VIII, O IX, Fe XIX and Fe XX for different gas densities and compared with the ionic concentrations for a plasma in photoionisation equilibrium (black stars).

Figure 3. Step-up light curve case: the first two panels show respectively the time-dependent evolution of the electron temperature and the heating and cooling (solid and dashed lines) rates for a grid of density values. In the third panel, we compare the shape of the heating curves dividing them by its dependency on the gas density. The bottom panel illustrates the contribution of the main heating and cooling processes for a plasma with $n_H = 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Figure 4. Step-down light curve case: the light curve is shown in the top panel. The ionising flux drops by a factor of ten in 0.01 s. In the panels below we show the time-dependent evolution of the concentration relative to hydrogen of O VIII, O IX, Fe XIX and Fe XX for different gas densities and compared with the ionic concentrations for a plasma in photoionisation equilibrium (black stars).

Figure 5. Step-down light curve case: the first two panels show respectively the time-dependent evolution of the electron temperature and the heating and cooling (solid and dashed lines) rates for a grid of density values. In the third panel, we compare the shape of the cooling curves dividing them by its dependency on the gas density. The bottom panel illustrates the contribution of the main heating and cooling processes for a plasma with $n_{\text{H}} = 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

501 In the *top* panel of Figure 5, we show how the plasma tem-
 502 perature drops as a function of time and density. As shown
 503 before, the temperature is driven by the difference between
 504 cooling (dashed lines) and heating rates (solid lines) shown
 505 in second panel. In this case, the cooling is larger than heat-
 506 ing and leads the temperature decrease. During the transition
 507 from high to low flux level, the cooling does not vary whereas
 508 the heating rate drops. As observed in the previous case, the
 509 change of the heating always happens at the same time inde-
 510 pendent of the gas density. After this jump, both cooling and
 511 heating rates stay steady for a time period that depends on the
 512 gas density: the lower the density the longer the steady phase.
 513 Then, both cooling and heating increase in the same manner
 514 until the cooling finally drops, reaching the same level of the
 515 heating. From this moment on, the gas is in photoionisation
 516 equilibrium with the ionising source.

517 The cooling rate curve has the same shape for different
 518 densities, but they are spread over different timescales, as
 519 shown in the third panel of Figure 5. In the bottom panel,
 520 we show the total cooling rate curve for a gas with density
 521 of $n_H = 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ with all the processes that contribute to
 522 it. Collisional excitation is the most important phenomenon
 523 and it is responsible for the bump observed at a later time
 524 in the total cooling curve. The ratios between the different
 525 contributions do not vary among the grid of densities consid-
 526 ered here. Photoionisation, Compton scattering and Auger
 527 electrons are, instead, the main heating processes.

528 It is now possible to compare the ionisation case, repre-
 529 sented by the step-up function, with the recombination case,
 530 described by step-down function. In the *top* and *bottom* panel
 531 of Figure 6, we juxtapose, respectively, the evolution of the
 532 O VIII concentrations and the plasma temperatures as a func-
 533 tion of $n_H \cdot \text{time}$. The two concentration curves follow shapes
 534 which are not the inverse of each other, as we might expect
 535 to see for a gas in photoionisation equilibrium. They both
 536 include a plateau phase which, as we have already seen in
 537 Figure 2 and Figure 4, is common to all the ionic species.

538 In the ionisation case (solid purple line), the concentration
 539 of O VIII reaches the plateau ten time faster than in the re-
 540 combination configuration (dashed light-blue line). The du-
 541 ration of the plateau and the following rise (or drop) of the
 542 ionic concentration depends on the late evolution of the tem-
 543 perature. In the recombination case, the temperature varies
 544 significantly quicker than the ionisation case and it reaches
 545 the equilibrium value in a shorter time. Consequently, the
 546 recombining ionic concentration shows a shorter flat phase
 547 and reaches the final equilibrium state around ten time faster
 548 than the ionising curve. This differences show the impor-
 549 tance of including the computation of the plasma temperature
 550 for an accurate time-dependent modelling of a photoionised
 551 plasma.

Figure 6. Comparison between the step-up and step-down scenarios. In the *top* panel, we show the evolution of the O VIII concentration as a function of $n_H \cdot t$. In the same rest-frame, the evolution of the plasma temperature is illustrated in the *bottom* panel.

3.4. Flaring light curve

552

553 The previous two scenarios explained in Section 3.2 and
 554 3.3 represents two didactic frameworks that help demonstrate
 555 the time-dependent effects on the ionic concentrations. In
 556 this section we present a more realistic case where the ion-
 557 ising continuum flares briefly as shown in the *top* panel of
 558 Figure 7. In detail, the ionising luminosity increases by a
 559 factor of 10 in 6 ks (between the first red and grey vertical
 560 dashed line), stays in high state for 3 ks (between the two
 561 grey dashed vertical lines) and subsequently decreases to low
 562 state again in 6 ks (between the second red and grey dashed
 563 vertical lines).

564

565 Using this flaring light curve, the SED shape of Mrk 509
 566 and ionisation parameter $\log \xi = 2.0$, we computed the time
 567 evolution of the ionic concentrations. In Figure 7, we show
 568 the concentration curves of O VIII, O IX, Fe XIX, Fe XX as a
 569 function of time and density. It is easy to distinguish in this
 570 case the three scenarios described in Section 2: 1) in gas with
 571 density above 10^8 cm^{-3} (yellow and orange shades) the ionic
 572 concentrations follow closely their *equilibrium* values (black
 573 stars); 2) when the density is between 10^6 cm^{-3} and 10^8 cm^{-3}
 574 (red-purple shades) the ionic concentrations are *delayed* and
 575 smooth with respect to the equilibrium curve; 3) the ionic

Figure 7. Flaring light curve case. The light curve is shown in the top panel. The ionising flux symmetrically increases and decreases by a factor of ten in 3 ks. The high state phase between the dashed grey vertical lines is 2 ks long. The onset and the end of flare are marked with two dashed red vertical lines. In the middle and bottom panels we show the time-dependent evolution of the concentration relative to hydrogen of O VIII, O IX, Fe XIX and Fe XX for different gas density values and compared with the ionic concentrations for a plasma in photoionisation equilibrium (black stars).

Figure 8. Flaring test case: the first two panels show respectively the time-dependent evolution of the electron temperature and the heating and cooling (solid and dashed lines) rates for a grid of density values. In the bottom panel we display the contribution of the main heating and cooling processes for a plasma with density $n_H = 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

575 concentrations of low-density gases, with $n_{\text{H}} < 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$
 576 (blue shades) are *steady* and do not vary significantly with
 577 time. The gas does not have enough time to respond to the
 578 initial increase of the ionising luminosity.

579 The time evolution of Fe XIX concentration follows a
 580 double-horn curve which differs from the bell shape of the
 581 other three ions illustrated. Its ionic distribution peaks during
 582 the increase and decrease phases, between which the ionic
 583 state becomes less populated in favour of Fe XX, as the ionizing
 584 flux reaches its maximum. We already saw this transition
 585 in the third plot of Figure 2 and 4 for the increasing and de-
 586 creasing luminosity phase, respectively.

587 The time evolution of the temperature is shown in the
 588 *top* panel of Figure 8. Only high-density plasmas (with
 589 $n_{\text{H}} > 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) significantly increase their temperature dur-
 590 ing the flare of the ionising luminosity. Moreover, the tem-
 591 perature peaks at a delayed time with respect to the flare.
 592 In the *middle* panel, we compare the total heating and cool-
 593 ing for the considered density grid. In this flaring scenario,
 594 the time-evolution of the heating and cooling strongly de-
 595 pends on the gas density. For instance, the cooling is steady
 596 for low-density gas, whereas it quickly varies in the densest
 597 plasmas. Instead, the heating rate starts to evolve similarly
 598 to the ionising radiation as soon as we consider low density
 599 gas. Even though we mimic a light curve where the ionis-
 600 ing flare is symmetric, we see that during the flare the heat-
 601 ing time is longer than its cooling time and dominates in gas
 602 with medium and low density ($n_{\text{H}} < 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-3}$). To reach
 603 their energetic equilibrium (i.e. cooling = heating), the low
 604 density gases require a longer time than the time interval il-
 605 lustrated here. This explain why the cooling and heating do
 606 not match at the right end of the plot. In the *bottom* panel,
 607 we show the main contribution of the different processes to
 608 the heating and cooling rates. Similarly to the step-up and
 609 step-down cases studied before, photoionisation is the main
 610 heating process, whereas collisional excitation together with
 611 radiative recombination and bremsstrahlung are the most rel-
 612 evant cooling phenomena.

613 3.5. Transmitted spectrum

614 In the final step of the `tpho` computation, all the ionic con-
 615 centrations are used to build the transmitted spectrum of the
 616 plasma. It comes as a multiplicative component and it can be
 617 used to characterise the evolution of the absorption features
 618 observed in the data. The code provides a transmitted spec-
 619 trum at each desired point of the light curve, e.g. when the
 620 X-ray spectrum of the source is available. Moreover, `SPEX`
 621 allows a simultaneous fit of multiple epochs, which helps to
 622 obtain stronger constraints on the density of the absorber.

623 The time-dependent effects influence the spectral shape of
 624 the X-ray transmission as a function of time. In Figure 9,
 625 we compare the evolution of the transmitted spectrum for a

626 plasma in photoionisation equilibrium (in black), calculated
 627 with the `pion` model and the one calculated with the new
 628 model `tpho`, which takes into account the time dependent ef-
 629 fects (in magenta). We illustrate the case of the flaring light-
 630 curve (see Section 3.4. For the calculation, we assumed an
 631 initial photoionisation equilibrium with an ionisation param-
 632 eter of $\log \xi = 1.8$ (the initial transmitted spectrum is shown
 633 with the black dotted line in the top panel), a column density
 634 of $N_{\text{H}} = 5 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, and a density of $n_{\text{H}} = 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and
 635 the SED of Mrk 509. This combination of assumption gives a
 636 system in the *delayed* state option. We extrapolated the spec-
 637 tra at four different intervals of the light curve shown on the
 638 right panel: in particular at the flare maximum (top panel),
 639 right after the flare (middle panel) and after a long period of
 640 steady-state (two bottom panels).

641 The comparison highlights the impact of the time-
 642 dependent effect on the X-ray transmission spectrum. The
 643 deviations from the equilibrium spectrum are larger during
 644 the flare activity when the flux varies rapidly. The plasma
 645 slowly responds to the rapid increase of the ionising lumi-
 646 nosity and it shows a lower ionisation state at the peak of
 647 the flare. The shape of the iron unresolved transitions array
 648 which produces prominent features in the 730 – 830 eV en-
 649 ergy range (15 – 17 Å) and the overall opacity represent the
 650 strongest differences between the two transmitted spectra in
 651 the first two extraction epochs. Before the third extraction
 652 epoch, due to the steady flux, the gas has time to recover the
 653 photoionisation equilibrium and the two X-ray transmissions
 654 become similar. The gas requires a longer time ($t \sim 75 \text{ ks}$) to
 655 fully recover the equilibrium (last epoch).

656 The density of the plasma controls the evolution of the
 657 ionic concentrations (see Figure 2, 4, and 7) and therefore the
 658 evolution of the X-ray transmission. The transmitted spec-
 659 trum of lower density gases changes slower than the one of
 660 higher density plasma. In Figure 10, we compare the trans-
 661 mitted spectrum at the peak of the flaring light curve (9 ks)
 662 for several densities and two different initial ionisation states
 663 ($\log \xi = 0.5$ on the top panel and $\log \xi = 1.8$ on the bottom
 664 panel). Regardless of the increase of the intrinsic luminosity,
 665 the X-ray transmission of gases with $n_{\text{H}} \lesssim 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ does not
 666 diverge from the initial state (dotted black line). The equi-
 667 librium timescale for these absorbers is significantly longer
 668 than the increasing period and therefore the absorber does
 669 not have enough time to respond to the luminosity variation.
 670 In contrast, plasmas with $n_{\text{H}} \gtrsim 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ respond almost
 671 simultaneously to the increase of the luminosity and they
 672 can be considered in photoionisation equilibrium (black solid
 673 line). Finally, the opacity of the plasma decreases signifi-
 674 cantly with increasing density. High-density gases can, in-
 675 deed, reach higher ionisation states due to their shorter equi-
 676 librium timescales.

Figure 9. Comparison between the X-ray transmission (line and continuum absorption) of a plasma in photoionisation equilibrium (black solid line) and in non-photoionisation equilibrium (magenta solid line). We assume a plasma with a density of $n_{\text{H}} = 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and an initial ionisation parameter of $\log \xi = 1.8$. We show the comparison at three different epochs: from top to bottom 9 ks, 18 ks, 50 ks and 75 ks which correspond to the black dashed lines in the light curve panel on the right. In the top panel we also plot the initial transmitted spectrum (black dotted line), right before the onset of the flare.

3.6. Caveats

677

678 At present, our time-dependent photoionisation model re-
 679 lies on a few assumptions. Firstly, the model considers the
 680 plasma in photoionisation equilibrium with the ionising lu-
 681 minosity at the starting point of the light curve ($t = 0$). This
 682 assumption is necessary to evaluate the temperature, the ini-
 683 tial ionic concentrations and heating and cooling rates of the

684 plasma. However, it is possible that an AGN outflow, for ex-
 685 ample, it is already in non-equilibrium with the X-ray emis-
 686 sion at the beginning of the observing campaign. This can in-
 687 troduce uncertainties on the response time of the plasma and
 688 consequently also on its inferred density. In order to limit this
 689 uncertainty, it is important to monitor the intrinsic luminos-
 690 ity for an extended time interval. The initial equilibrium can

Figure 10. X-ray transmission of an absorber assuming different densities (10^5 cm^{-3} in red, 10^7 cm^{-3} in turquoise, and 10^9 cm^{-3} in orange) and initial ionisation parameters ($\log \xi = 0.5$ top panel and $\log \xi = 1.8$ bottom panel). We extracted all the spectra at the peak of the flaring light curve ($t = 9$ ks, see Figure 9). In both panels we overplot the initial transmitted spectrum ($t = 0$, black dotted line) and the spectrum of a plasma in photoionisation equilibrium with the ionising source at $t = 9$ ks (black solid line).

Figure 11. Impact of the ionising SED on the transmitted spectrum. In the top panel we compare the X-ray transmission of two plasmas with a different ionising SED and with the same initial ionising parameter and density: black line represents the transmittance for a plasma which does not vary the SED shape instead the yellow line shows the transmittance of a gas that sees an increase of the power-law index by 20%. The deviation between the two models is shown in the bottom panel.

691 be placed after a long phase of steady flux where the ionised
692 plasma is most likely in photoionisation equilibrium.

693 Moreover, we neglect any change of the SED components
694 such as the power-law slope, extent of the soft excess, re-
695 flection, or the optical/UV bump during the considered time.
696 The shape of the SED is kept frozen during the calculation
697 of the ionic concentration evolution. Only the total normal-
698 isation varies in correspondence with the ionising luminos-
699 ity. Therefore, the model is particularly suitable to describe
700 the time-dependent effects of AGN that do not show a strong
701 variability of the SED shape.

702 Differences in the ionising SED have direct impact on the
703 ionising balance and the thermal stability of photoionised
704 plasmas (Mehdipour et al. 2016). However, the changes in
705 the transmitted spectrum are limited to small changes of the
706 ionising SED. In Figure 11, we compare the transmitted spec-
707 tra considering (orange) and ignoring (black) any variation of
708 the spectral shape. In detail, we let the power-law index, Γ
709 increasing by 20% (from 1.9 to 2.3) and calculated the trans-
710 mitted spectrum at the flaring peak ($t = 9$ ks, see Figure 9).
711 We assumed a density of $n_{\text{H}} = 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and an initial ion-

712 isation parameter of $\log \xi = 1.8$. The deviation between the
713 two models is shown in percentage in the bottom panel. The
714 discrepancies are within 5%, which can be neglected with
715 the current high-resolution X-ray spectrometers. In a future
716 version of the code we will implement a more sophisticated
717 algorithm able to take into account any change of the ionising
718 SED.

719 We consider only optically thin slab of plasma where the
720 propagation time of the X-ray radiation is smaller than both
721 the source variability timescale and the associated recombi-
722 nation timescale (see Schwarzschild et al. 1972; Binette 1988). We
723 neglect any time-dependence of the radiative transfer which
724 becomes important for optically thick plasma (see García
725 et al. 2013). Recently, Sadoula et al. (2022) extensively stud-
726 ied the evolution of the ion fraction and temperature at vari-
727 ous depths in the cloud solving the time-dependent radiative
728 transfer equation. They show the relevance of this effect for
729 clouds with a thickness of 10^{16-17} cm . We refer to their work
730 for a detailed comparison between the time-dependent effects
731 of ionisation balance and the ones of the radiative transfer.

732 Finally, the present model assumes that all ions are in
 733 their ground state. This is good enough as far as total time-
 734 dependent ionization/recombination rates are computed. At
 735 high density many of the levels of ground terms and configu-
 736 rations become populated by collisions leading to population
 737 of metastable levels (Kallman et al. 2021). The critical den-
 738 sity leading to population of the excited levels is $\sim 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$
 739 (Mauche et al. 2004). For higher densities this would give
 740 obviously some deviations in the computed time-dependent
 741 ion concentrations, but not by large amounts since the main
 742 effect of the density is setting the proper time scales. Level
 743 populations are not computed, because that requires much
 744 more computational effort. Thus, for higher densities, the
 745 ion concentrations are reasonable, but obviously care should
 746 be taken with the absorption spectra (which are computed as-
 747 suming all ions are in the ground state).

748 4. DISCUSSION

749 Standard photoionisation models such as SPEX, CLOUDY
 750 (Ferland et al. 2017) and XSTAR (Bautista & Kallman 2001)
 751 allow us to characterise astrophysical plasma in ionisation
 752 equilibrium. This equilibrium assumption is valid in pres-
 753 ence of a steady ionising luminosity or when modelling high-
 754 density plasmas. A sudden variation of the ionising luminos-
 755 ity can cause departure from the photoionisation equilibrium.
 756 The equilibrium timescale (see Equation 2) indicates the time
 757 necessary for the plasma to recover the ionisation balance.
 758 When this timescale is similar to or longer than the ionis-
 759 ing source variability timescales the gas is non-equilibrium
 760 photoionisation with the ionising radiation. In other words,
 761 the assumption that heating and cooling rates are equal is not
 762 valid any more and time-dependent effects should be taken
 763 into account (e.g., Krolik & Kriss 1995; Nicastro et al. 1999).
 764 `tpho`, our new photoionisation model based on `pion`, in-
 765 cludes the time-dependence of all ionising/heating and re-
 766 combining/cooling processes in the plasma. The model is
 767 able to characterise the ionisation state of a plasma pho-
 768 toionised by a variable source. The full atomic database of
 769 SPEX is used to calculate the evolution of all the ionic species
 770 by solving the differential Equation 1.

771 Earlier time-dependent photoionisation codes used only
 772 limited atomic data to study the evolution of absorption fea-
 773 tures of low-resolution X-ray spectra. For example Nicastro
 774 et al. (1999) characterised the high signal-to-noise *ROSAT*
 775 observation of the Seyfert I galaxy NGC 4051 omitting pho-
 776 toionisation from the L shell and all the iron ions. This
 777 introduced uncertainties on the computation of the abun-
 778 dance balance of low ionised gases and a possible overes-
 779 timation of the O and Ne K shell photoionisation. Morales
 780 et al. (2000) studied the complex time behaviour of the oxy-
 781 gen absorption features detected in the *ASCA* and *BeppoSAX*
 782 spectra of MCG-6-30-15 using code developed by Reynolds

783 (1996) limited to only oxygen ions. High-resolution *Chan-*
 784 *dra*/HETG (Canizares et al. 2005) and *XMM-Newton*/RGS
 785 (den Herder et al. 2001) spectra require an extended atomic
 786 model in order to analyse the variability of the whole forest
 787 of absorption lines. To study the variability of the absorbers
 788 along the line of sight of Mrk 509 Kaastra et al. (2012) used
 789 CLOUDY to generate several time-dependent photoionisation
 790 models for a grid of densities.

791 By implementing our `tpho` model for the SPEX package
 792 we do not only have direct access to the SPEX database and
 793 photoionisation routines, but we can generate the transmitted
 794 spectrum which can be promptly multiplied with the broad-
 795 band model. As a results, it is possible to directly fit the
 796 data and constrain the density of the absorber. The model
 797 is therefore suitable to study the time behaviour of the ab-
 798 sorption features detected in the high-resolution spectra taken
 799 with current and future X-ray missions.

800 It is also possible to extend the time-dependent photoion-
 801 isation modelling to high-resolution spectra in the UV band
 802 (e.g., Arav et al. 2020). In case the absorber has spectral
 803 features in both the UV and X-ray band and both spectra
 804 are available, a simultaneous UV/X-ray analysis would accu-
 805 rately determine the time-dependent properties of the plasma.
 806 Finally, the `tpho` model can be used to verify the density es-
 807 timates from metastable lines in both UV and X-ray energy
 808 bands.

809 The primary scientific targets of the `tpho` model are the
 810 outflows observed in bright Seyfert I galaxies. The code al-
 811 lows to study the time behaviour of both low and high ion-
 812 isation plasma, tuning their flow and dispersion velocities,
 813 relative abundances, and column density. The main informa-
 814 tion we can access with the `tpho` model is the density of the
 815 absorber. The time-dependent effects strongly depend on this
 816 quantity (see Section 2). Consequently, by reliably deriving
 817 the density of the plasma, it is possible to accurately locate
 818 the outflows and derive their energetics.

819 Moreover, the time variable spectra provided by `tpho` can
 820 be used to predict the effect of warm absorber or obscura-
 821 tion events on the time lags and coherence of the energy de-
 822 pendent light curves. The response of the gas to changes
 823 in the ionising continuum can indeed introduce additional
 824 lags (Silva et al. 2016). Thus, recognising the contribution
 825 of the recombining gas to the AGN X-ray time lags is cru-
 826 cial to interpret the continuum lags connected to propagation
 827 and reflection effects in the inner emitting regions. Recently,
 828 Juráňová et al. (2022) demonstrated that the gas response to
 829 the source radiation results in a decrease of the coherence in
 830 the Fourier timing analysis which can be used to constrain the
 831 gas density, opening therefore a new methodology to derive
 832 the location of outflows.

833 Tidal-disruption events (TDEs) and gamma-ray bursts
 834 (GRBs) represent two potential astrophysical systems where

Figure 12. Time-dependent effects in a synthetic RGS and *Arcus* spectra of an AGN (SED from Mrk 509) with a warm absorber in absorption. To simulate the data we computed the time-dependent photoionisation model 25 ks after a sharp increase of the ionising luminosity. In red, we show the best fit using a pion component and neglecting the time-dependent effects. The residuals are displayed in the bottom panels. The best fit using two pion components is shown in green.

Figure 13. Time-dependent effects in a synthetic XRISM spectra of an AGN (SED from Mrk 509) with a warm absorber in absorption. To simulate the data we computed the time-dependent photoionisation model 25 ks after a sharp increase of the ionising luminosity. In red, we show the best fit using a pion component and neglecting the time-dependent effects. The residuals are displayed in the bottom panels. The best-fit using two pion components is shown in green.

835 a time-dependent photoionisation modelling can be applied.
 836 In these transient events, the drastic increase of luminos-
 837 ity photoionises the surrounding gas (either ejecta or host
 838 galaxy); the explosive phase is then followed by a rapid de-
 839 crease of the flux where the gas recombines on timescales

840 determined by the density. The variability study of the ab-
 841 sorption features in the spectra of such extreme events is,
 842 however, limited by the collecting area and the slow capabil-
 843 ity of current X-ray telescopes. Absorption lines are hardly
 844 detected even in the X-ray spectrum of the brightest GRBs
 845 (Campana et al. 2016) and only a few luminous TDEs show
 846 spectral features imprinted by an outflow (Miller et al. 2015).
 847 Future X-ray missions, in particular *Athena*, will likely en-
 848 able time-dependent photoionisation modelling of these ex-
 849 treme astrophysical events (Piro et al. 2021).

4.1. Simulation

850
 851 We discuss here the impact of the time-dependent effects
 852 on a standard time-resolved X-ray spectroscopy campaign of
 853 AGN outflows. In Figure 10, we demonstrate how the shape
 854 of the transmission spectrum of a warm absorber calculated
 855 with our *tpho* model strongly diverges from the equilibrium
 856 one depending on the density of the plasma. We now in-
 857 vestigate how well a standard photoionisation model can de-
 858 scribe the spectral features of a gas in non-equilibrium with
 859 the ionising source. We aim to answer the question: is a
 860 time-dependent photoionisation model really necessary to fit
 861 the AGN outflow spectra?

862 To address this question we simulated the absorbed spec-
 863 trum of an AGN after a sudden increase in the intrinsic lumi-
 864 nosity by a factor of ten. In specific, we used the step-up light
 865 curve presented in the top panel of Figure 2 and we extracted
 866 the spectrum computed by our *tpho* model at $t = 25$ ks after
 867 the jump. As for the initial conditions, we assumed the SED
 868 of Mrk 509 and a warm absorber with density $n_{\text{H}} = 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$,

869 column density $N_{\text{H}} = 5 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, ionisation parameter
 870 $\log \xi = 1$, and outflow velocity $v_{\text{out}} = -300 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. We sim-
 871 ulated the signal-to-noise ratio expected for a 50 ks observa-
 872 tion taken with XMM-Newton/RGS. The synthetic spectrum
 873 contains the time-dependent effects and it is shown in the up-
 874 per left panel of Figure 12. Following the common photoion-
 875 isation modelling procedure, we fit the absorption features of
 876 the warm absorber adding a `pion` component and setting the
 877 N_{H} , $\log \xi$ and v_{out} as free parameters. The best fit, shown with
 878 a solid red line, favours a warm absorber component with
 879 a higher ionisation parameter of 1.6. We obtained a worse
 880 statistic ($\Delta C\text{-stat} = 60$) and significant residuals around the
 881 iron UTA, as shown in the left bottom panel. To correct for
 882 these residuals we added a second `pion` component (best fit
 883 in green). The fit statistic improved by $\Delta C\text{-stat} = 22$ for three
 884 free parameters and two absorbers with $\log \xi$ of 1.3 and 2.0
 885 and similar column density are found. It is thus important
 886 to include the time-dependent effects in the photoionisation
 887 modelling of AGN outflow.

888 For modelling extremely variable sources, time-
 889 independent photoionisation models may not be sufficiently
 890 accurate. In some cases, they might erroneously indicate the
 891 presence of a larger number of absorber components with
 892 respect to a time-dependent photoionisation analysis. As we
 893 have shown in Section 3.1, the ionic concentrations follow
 894 different time evolutions based on the density and ionisation
 895 state of the gas. Thus, during specific epochs (e.g. after a
 896 strong variation of the intrinsic luminosity), it is not possible
 897 to reproduce the spectrum of a gas in non-equilibrium with
 898 a standard photoionisation modelling and the best-fitting
 899 would show residuals around some spectral features. These
 900 discrepancies will become more significant with the advent
 901 of the new generation of high-resolution X-ray instruments.

902 We repeat the same analysis using the up-to-date response
 903 matrix of the mission concept *Arcus* which is expected to
 904 reach a resolving power of $R=3800$ in the waveband 10–60 Å
 905 and an effective area of 325 cm² at 19 Å. To simulate the
 906 response of the instrument, we followed the detailed guide²
 907 written by the *Arcus* team. Due to its large effective area
 908 (325 cm² at 19 Å) and resolution power in the soft X-ray
 909 band ($R = 3800$), *Arcus* would represent a powerful instru-
 910 ment to study how AGN outflows respond to any luminosity
 911 variation. It will revolutionise current photoionisation mod-
 912 elling approaches as *Chandra* and XMM-Newton did in the
 913 early 2000s.

914 In the top right panel of Figure 12, we show the *Arcus* syn-
 915 thetic spectrum computed using the same set-up and expo-
 916 sure time described above. The plot of the residual shows a
 917 strong discrepancy in the Fe UTA band which neither a sin-

918 gle nor a multi steady-state component can reproduce. By
 919 not including the time-dependent effects in the modelling,
 920 the C -statistics of the best fit decrease by $\Delta C\text{-stat} \sim 1600$.
 921 In presence of a variable photoionising source it will be cru-
 922 cial to include the time-dependent effects in the modelling of
 923 the absorbing plasma.

924 The X-ray Imaging and Spectroscopy Mission (*XRISM*;
 925 Tashiro et al. 2018) represents the next high-resolution X-ray
 926 telescope to be launched in 2023. The soft band of the syn-
 927 thetic spectrum obtained with the X-ray micro-calorimeter
 928 *Resolve* (Ishisaki et al. 2018) is shown in 13. Similarly to
 929 the previous cases, `pion` cannot characterise correctly the
 930 absorption features linked to an ionised outflow which is
 931 in a non-equilibrium photoionisation state. The statistic of
 932 the best fit decreases by $\Delta C\text{-stat} \sim 900$ with respect to the
 933 best fit obtained with `tpho`. In this case, adding a second
 934 `pion` component significantly improves the overall best fit
 935 ($\Delta C\text{-stat} \sim 170$) as the residual highlights in the bottom panel
 936 of Figure 13.

937 5. SUMMARY

938 Density represents a crucial physical quantity in modelling
 939 of photoionised plasmas and ascertaining the energetics of
 940 AGN outflows. In general, standard photoionisation models
 941 that assume a gas in constant ionisation equilibrium do not
 942 take into account time-dependent effects in the plasma. In
 943 the present work we have shown the impact of the density
 944 on the ionisation state of a gas photoionised by a variable
 945 source. Each ion has a specific recombination and photoioni-
 946 sation timescales which depend on both the ionisation state of
 947 the plasma and its density. When the gas is not in ionisation
 948 balance, i.e. when the $t_{\text{eq}} \lesssim t_{\text{var}}$, the shape of the transmit-
 949 ted spectrum is significantly affected by the time-dependent
 950 photoionisation effects.

951 We developed a new time-dependent photoionisation
 952 model, `tpho`, which has already been implemented and pub-
 953 licly released with `SPEX` v. 3.07. The model reads as input the
 954 light curve and the ionising SED and computes the time evo-
 955 lution of the ionic concentrations and transmitted spectrum
 956 of a specific plasma (n_{H} , $\log \xi$, N_{H} , v_{out} , v_{turb}). The primary
 957 goals of `tpho` are:

- 958 • *to characterise the time-dependent effects.* We demon-
 959 strated that in presence of a variable ionising source if
 960 the time dependent effects are taken into account the
 961 warm absorber spectral features can be explained by
 962 a single components instead of multiple steady-state
 963 phases. Implementing the time-dependent effects in
 964 the photoionisation modelling of AGN outflow is es-
 965 sential with the advent of new X-ray missions (e.g.,
 966 *XRISM* and *Arcus*).
- 967 • *to constrain the absorber density and location.* Know-
 968 ing the distance of the different absorbing clouds from

² <http://www.arcusxray.org/responses/OverallGuide.pdf>

969 the ionising source enables us to map the AGN out-
 970 flows and to determine their energetics. Applying the
 971 `tpho` model to a sample of bright Seyfert I galaxies
 972 which show the presence of outflows can provide im-
 973 portant insights on the AGN feedback driven by the
 974 outflows and possibly understand the relation between
 975 ultra-fast outflows, warm absorbers and molecular out-
 976 flows.

977 Future X-ray telescopes will allow accurate time-dependent
 978 photoionisation modelling of plasma in the presence of vari-
 979 able ionising sources. In particular, low-density, ionised out-
 980 flows of variable AGN will require a model that is able to
 981 characterise the time-effects. Long monitoring campaigns of
 982 bright Seyfert I galaxies will not only help to map the out-
 983 flows along the line of sight but also to better understand their
 984 launch mechanism and to estimate the mass and energy that
 985 they carry.

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1001 *Software:* The `tpho` model has been implemented in the
 1002 X-ray fitting program `SPEX` (Kaastra et al. 2022) v 3.07 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6948884>).
 1003

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